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Status Quo of Mental Health Services of Selected Barangays in Bacoor: Basis in the Development of Public Mental Health Poster

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Abstract

This study aims to expand the understanding of mental health, its importance, and the promotion of mental health services within barangays in the Philippines. 16 barangay healthcare workers in Bacoor City participated in a questionnaire survey, with five individuals undergoing follow-up interviews. The researcher used a self-made 5-point Likert-scale to measure the level and relationship of accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services. The findings of this study revealed a significant positive correlation among the key factors of applicability, awareness, and accessibility of mental health services. This correlation underscores the potential for substantial enhancements in mental health services through targeted interventions.

Keywords: *accessibility, applicability, awareness, barangay mental health services, public mental health*

Introduction

As of August 2023, the City Government of Bacoor has no city ordinances or resolutions that specifically support mental health programs in the city. In October 2023, a telepsychology program called Strike as One Telepayo was implemented in the city. In November 2023, the city conducted a two-day psychological training for health workers (City Government of Bacoor, 2023). Other short-term programs such as mental health seminars are conducted on relative occasions. Several studies have shown positive conditions of mental health in Bacoor. A study by Tolosa (2021) revealed that college students in Bacoor had positive mental health well-being despite the situation brought upon by the COVID-19 pandemic. Valledor (2023) also noted that the elderly in Bacoor City, despite the stereotypical assumptions, were well-informed in mental health due to different channels such as media and community programs.

However, studies exhibiting negative findings about mental health in Bacoor have also emerged. Dayrit (2022) concluded that during the COVID-19 pandemic, female psychology students had low quality of life while male psychology students had low social relationships. Martinez (2022) showcased how members of the Office of Senior Citizens Association in Bacoor, Cavite have thoughts of worthlessness despite enthusiastic engagement in community and church activities.

These contradicting findings from various studies on the mental health outcomes in Bacoor have vague indications on the current conditions of mental health services in the City. While the wealth of research on the mental health of individuals or groups in Bacoor exists, the status quo of mental health services is less understood.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe public mental health (PMH) through the assessment of the accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services among the selected Barangays in Bacoor. This study also aimed to develop a community poster outlining the status quo of mental health services based on the assessment. This study seeks to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the health officials in terms of: barangay, occupation, and gender?
2. What is the level of accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services of Barangays in Bacoor City?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services of Barangays in Bacoor City?
4. How do barangays in Bacoor integrate the accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services?

Literature Review

Mental Health Service Accessibility, Awareness, and Applicability

According to the studies of Radez et al. (2020) seeking and accessing help is related to stigma and embarrassment, lack of mental health knowledge and negative perceptions about help seeking. Moreover, accessing help through digital tools is not promoted and facilitated. In an article by Lattie et al. (2022), recommendations were provided in the improvement of the accessibility of digital mental health services. There is significance in designing digital mental health interventions with consideration of evidence-based approaches.

Moreover, integration of psychological crisis intervention was recommended by Wen et al. (2022) in reducing the negative outcomes brought about by COVID-19. The interventions were guided and implemented by trained mental health professionals and expert teams in provinces and municipalities. In addition to this, educational articles/videos were uploaded for the general public to have knowledge regarding mental health.

In an evaluation of mental health programs in Northern Samar, Jumadiao-Rojo (2023) stated that implementers of mental health programs include mental health nurses, municipal health officers, and barangay health workers (BHWs). These implementers possess qualifications and expertise through training and seminars. Through these implementers, the mental health program in Northern Samar was concluded to be moderately implemented.

Furthermore, a study by Putri et al. (2021) emphasized that the government does not pay much attention to mental health issues/problems due to the small number of government policies implemented for mental health compared to those of physical health problems/issues.

Mental Health Services at Barangay-level

As grassroot units, barangay-level mental health services are integral in mental health awareness. In Barangay Guinhawa in Bulacan, Santos et al. (2019) stated that the demographic profile of residents is significant in mental health awareness. In a barangay with a moderate level of awareness, residents who were employed, female, divorced, and aged 21-25 were shown to be more aware of issues in mental health.

In the same vein of awareness, Dela Cruz et al. (2020) conducted a study about mental health knowledge, attitude, and behavior in Barangay Tibagan in San Juan City. They concluded that the residents were generally knowledgeable and accepting towards mental health illnesses. The respondents were also shown to be less stigmatizing and a willing attitude to interact with people with mental health illness.

Feliciano (2023) stated that health professionals are crucial in the integration of mental health to primary care, with distinction to Barangay Health Workers (BHWs).

Deguma (2023) explored the essence of BHWs as informal caregivers of mental health. It is recommended for LGUs to provide necessary support to BHWs. In terms of healthcare delivery, communication with BHWs is an important factor.

Similarly, Camasin et al. (2023) emphasized that BHWs are utilizing effective strategies of face-to-face communication. Still, support for virtual communication strategies is needed to deliver communication methods inclusively especially with the advent of technology.

Public Mental Health Intervention

In a review by Castillo et al. (2019), three key assumptions were determined regarding community interventions. The first includes recognizing the diverse influences that exist at various social-ecological levels. The second focuses on investing in the participation of the community to provide resources and insights beyond the healthcare system. The third centers on the prioritization of community mental health and social outcomes.

Campion (2022) defined public mental health (PMH) as taking a “population approach to mental health which includes assessment and strategic decisions to improve coverage, outcomes and coordination of different levels of mental disorder prevention and mental wellbeing promotion.” PMH intends to improve mental healthcare by working with a range of public, third sector, other organizations, local communities, and individuals. Evidence-based public mental health interventions provide preventive measures, treatment options, and the ability to mitigate related consequences while promoting mental wellbeing. Importantly, many of these interventions are not only cost-effective but also economically beneficial.

Additionally, Strategic plans to increase the availability of mental health experts are important. This includes hiring more mental health workers, including those who can handle specialty needs, and utilizing virtual technology to get around physical limitations (Moroz et al., (2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This research used a mixed-method type of design. According to George (2021) a mixed-method research blends quantitative and qualitative data in providing results for the research question.

Respondents

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of barangay, occupation, and gender. Each barangay contributes at approximately 6.3% to the total. There are a total of 16 barangays and each barangay appears once in the distribution, indicating that there are no duplicates or repetitions in the data. Among the occupations listed, Barangay Health Worker (BHW) is the most dominant, with 5 individuals accounting for 31.3% of the sample, followed closely by 4 Nurses representing 25% of the sample, and Midwife I with 2 individuals (12.5%).

Other occupations such as City Health Office Midwife, generic Midwife, Midwife II, Nurse II, and Physician are each represented by 1 individual, making up smaller proportions of the sample ranging from 6.3% to 6.3%. In terms of gender, the respondents are made up of 12 female (75%) and 4 male (25%).

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Demographic Profile</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Barangay	Habay 1	1	6.3
	Ligas	1	6.3
	Mambog 2	1	6.3
	Mambog 3	1	6.3
	Mambog 4	1	6.3
	Molino 1	1	6.3
	Molino 2	1	6.3
	Molino 5	1	6.3
	Molino 6	1	6.3
	P.F. Espiritu 1	1	6.3
	P.F. Espiritu 5	1	6.3
	P.F. Espiritu 6	1	6.3
	Queen's Row Central	1	6.3
	Salinas 2	1	6.3
	Talaba 2	1	6.3
	Zapote 3	1	6.3
	Total	16	100.0
Occupation	BHW	5	31.3
	CHO Midwife	1	6.3
	Midwife	1	6.3
	Midwife I	2	12.5
	Midwife II	1	6.3
	Nurse	4	25.0
	Nurse II	1	6.3
	Physician	1	6.3
	Total	16	100.0
Gender	Male	12	75.0
	Female	4	25.0
	Total	16	100.0

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents in terms of barangay, occupation, and gender. Each barangay contributes at approximately 6.3% to the total. There are a total of 16 barangays and each barangay appears once in the distribution, indicating that there are no duplicates or repetitions in the data. Among the occupations listed, Barangay Health Worker (BHW) is the most dominant, with 5 individuals accounting for 31.3% of the sample, followed closely by 4 Nurses representing 25% of the sample, and Midwife I with 2 individuals (12.5%). Other occupations such as City Health Office Midwife, generic Midwife, Midwife II, Nurse II, and Physician are each represented by 1 individual, making up smaller proportions of the sample ranging from 6.3% to 6.3%. In terms of gender, the respondents are made up of 12 female (75%) and 4 male (25%).

Instrument

A self-made survey questionnaire was prepared for this research. The questionnaire had three (3) subscales, which include a.) accessibility, b.) awareness, and c.) applicability of mental health services. Each subscale had ten (10) items, with the whole questionnaire having a total of thirty (30) items. The items were in positive statements to practically measure the levels of the factors. Likert scale was utilized, and subjects were expected to respond using the following values: 1 - Strongly Agree, 2 - Agree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Disagree, 5 - Strongly Disagree. For each subscale, two qualitative interview questions were also prepared.

Table 2. *Reliability Statistics*

	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
Accessibility	0.919	10
Awareness	0.924	10
Applicability	0.945	10
Total	0.969	30

Procedure

The distribution of the demographic profile of the participants was analyzed in terms of barangay, occupation, and gender. Then, the level of each of the factors (accessibility, awareness, and applicability) was analyzed and interpreted using mean and standard deviation analysis. The relationship of these factors was also analyzed using multiple correlation analysis. Finally, the interview responses were

analyzed using thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of St. Dominic College of Asia based on the compliance with the minimum standards of the SDCA Research Guidelines. Respondents were deployed based on their willingness to participate in this study with informed consent.

Results and Discussion

Table 3. *The Level of Accessibility of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Accessibility	3.1188	1.4724	Neutral

The Level of Accessibility of Mental Health Services in the barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite had a general assessment of 3.1188 (SD=1.4724), which was verbally interpreted as “Neutral.”

Table 4. *The Level of Awareness of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Awareness	3.0563	1.1677	Neutral

The Level of Awareness of Mental Health Services in the barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite had a general assessment of 3.0563 (SD=1.1677), which was verbally interpreted as “Neutral.”

Table 5. *The Level of Applicability of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite*

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Applicability	3.1813	1.2894	Neutral

The Level of Applicability of Mental Health Services in the barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite had a general assessment of 3.1813 (SD=1.2894), which was verbally interpreted as “Neutral.”

Table 6. *Multiple Correlational Analysis of Accessibility, Awareness, & Applicability of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite*

	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Remarks	Decision
Accessibility, Awareness, & Applicability	0.784	0.002	Strong, Positive Correlation	Significant	Reject Ho

The multiple correlational analysis of the Level of Accessibility, Awareness, & Applicability of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite show that the relationship between the 3 factors has a strong, positive correlation with a correlation coefficient of 0.784 and a p-value of 0.002, which is significant at 5 percent level.

Table 7. *Thematic Analysis of the Accessibility, Awareness, & Applicability of Mental Health Services in the Barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite*

Major Themes	Sub Themes
Accessibility	Reliance on referrals Limited facilities and infrastructures Specialized services
Awareness	Awareness and education of the general public Coordination with schools’ psychological departments
Applicability	Support from LGU for resources and information improvement Health worker training

Accessibility, awareness, and applicability emerged as major themes.

For accessibility, three sub-themes were identified: reliance on referrals, limited facilities and infrastructure, and specialized services. The barangay health centers recognize the significance of referrals and coordination with other institutions, such as City Health Offices and specialized clinics, to ensure that individuals requiring mental health support are directed to the appropriate facilities. This is highlighted in these quotes:

“More on referrals kami... Barangay ang naghahatid sa pag checheckup sa CHO o kaya sa mga clinic.” (Respondent 1).

“Nagre-refer [ng mental health cases] sa CSWD.” (Respondent 2).

“In the health center, consultation pa lang. Mostly, referral pa lang.” (Respondent 4).

The lack of proper facilities, such as the absence of counseling areas, hinders the accessibility of mental health services. The need for such areas is proven as follows:

“Kailangan ng awareness muna. If ever, maka-provide ng facility.” (Respondent 2).

“Not ready to accept, no time due to the amount of patients... There should be area of counseling... Devoted place for counseling.” (Respondent 4).

For some health centers with psychological care training, targeted support for disaster victims and trauma response are offered. These specialized services are indicated in the following quotes:

“Training [was] more on psychological trauma.” (Respondent 3).

“If there are victims of fire, typhoon, or other disasters. They offer counseling— one-on-one. To identify their mental state.” (Respondent 5).

Two sub-themes were identified for awareness: awareness and education of the general public and coordination with schools' psychological departments.

Moreover, there is a strong emphasis on mental health awareness and education, with suggestions for conducting seminars, workshops, and community-level discussions to raise awareness and encourage support for mental health issues. This is proven by the following quotes:

“Seminars on mental health can be conducted... Pwedeng mag-offer ng lectures.” (Respondent 2).

“Assisting patients and how to handle them. Pasensya muna at minsan, ipapaliwanag ang mental health sa kanila.” (Respondent 3).

“A community-level discussion to know the community's state of mental well-being.” (Respondent 5).

Collaboration with academic institutions' psychology departments and other relevant entities is also advisable to enhance understanding and support for individuals with mental health conditions. This is proven as follows:

“They attend lectures and collaborate with other institutions like universities in [Social] Hygiene [Clinic]... Collaborate with schools with psychological department to expose psych students and also benefit both parties.” (Respondent 4).

“...Willing to undergo training to learn more techniques and tools to help mentally ill patients.” (Respondent 5).

For applicability, two sub themes were identified: support from LGU for resources and information improvement and health worker training.

Despite resource and infrastructural constraints, barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite acknowledge the significance of ongoing training, education, and collaboration in fostering accessible, well-informed, and practical mental health services within their communities. This is highlighted in the following quotes:

“Broad kasi [ang mental health]. Hindi ito nadi-discuss sa health center... walang pumupunta na patients.” (Respondent 1).

“What's needed are support from LGUs to gain more information to handle cases.” (Respondent 5).

However, there is a notable gap in training for barangay health workers and personnel in mental health services or psychological first aid. This is highlighted as follows:

“Trainings on psychological first aid. Pero ilang days lang 'yon eh.” (Respondent 3).

“In the level of health center, doctors, nurses, and midwives are trained in psychological first aid... The lectures or sessions are continuous.” (Respondent 4).

The findings revealed that in the level of accessibility, there are certain aspects of mental health services that are available, such as hotlines and emergency services. However, there is room for improvement to increase the accessibility of these services via digital platforms.

The thematic analysis that was conducted on the qualitative data revealed that in the aforementioned barangays, the health officials rely on referrals to external facilities like the City Health Offices or private clinics specializing in mental health services. Some barangays offer specialized services, like counseling for disaster and/or trauma victims, suggesting a need for tailored mental health support.

The findings of Lattie et al. (2022) and Camasin et al. (2023) emphasized the relevance of virtual technology in the accessibility of mental health services.

In contrast, the accessibility of mental health services through digital and virtual means in this study had less support. However, hotlines for mental health concerns are accessible. This availability of emergency crisis hotlines can be attributed to the established hotline

systems of the barangay. These hotline systems are highly advised at community-level, as supported by Jung and Jun (2020), who also stated the importance of response teams alongside.

The findings further reveal that in the level of awareness, policy implementation is effective, but there are areas requiring improvement such as awareness campaigns. Thematic analysis shows that joint efforts with the CHO and private clinics aimed to increase mental health awareness and facilitate educational activities like workshops and seminars. Recognizing the crucial role of mental health awareness in increasing community support and understanding, awareness campaigns through seminars, workshops, and community-level discussions are highly recommended.

Furthermore, the results suggest the need for mental health awareness and education. The organization of awareness campaigns is highlighted as an area for improvement and other activities such as seminars and workshops are highly recommended, which are supported by the findings of Radez et al. (2021), in order to reduce stigma and enhance awareness and understanding of mental health. In a similar association, Jung & Jun (2020) claimed that the distribution of leaflets is encouraged in promoting mental health. The distribution of flyers for mental health awareness suggests a neutral score in this study, however, a plausible conclusion is that such materials are unavailable as none of the respondents were able to show any samples. The notable gap in training for barangay health workers and personnel in mental health services or psychological first aid was recommended to be addressed. This is aligned with the evaluation of Jumadiao-Rojo (2023) in which the implementers of mental health programs such as nurses, municipal health officers, and BHWs gain expertise through seminars and training.

Regarding the level of applicability of mental health services, findings suggest that there are positive aspects like efficient patient referral coordination, but there are challenges in relation to the allocation of funds for mental health initiatives. In increasing the budgetary support, also improves the overall applicability of mental health services. There is also an observed limitation in the resources and infrastructure. However, there is an observed gap in training for barangay health workers and personnel in mental health services and/or psychological first aid. Consistent training for health workers in Psychological First Aid and other various mental health care techniques is also just as important. Furthermore, collaborations with educational institutions and their psychological departments are recommended to broaden knowledge and support for individuals with mental health issues. Overall, support from Local Government Units (LGUs) is emphasized as essential for the improvement of awareness and resource availability to effectively address mental health cases.

As shown in this study, coordination with other institutions, continuous training, and specialized services for mental health are highly proposed. These proposals are highly essential for BHWs, as supported by Deguma (2023) in which BHWs are recommended as informal caregivers of mental healthcare.

These results provide insights into the relationship between accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services as determinants of the status quo. This data supports the claims of Campion (2022) that public mental health produces intervention measures, treatment options, and mental well-being promotion.

Conclusions

This research found that the status quo of mental health services in selected barangays in Bacoor City, Cavite still needs improvements. The accessibility, awareness, and applicability of mental health services collectively had a neutral level. In terms of integration, mental health services had notable gaps in each factor. For accessibility, the extent of mental health services relied heavily on referrals. Despite the availability of teleconsultation programs such as the Telepayo, digital access, and virtual technology still had notable gaps in barangay health centers. For awareness, there was a significant call for campaigns and partnerships with educational institutions. For applicability, training and seminars were conducted for the health workers/officials but they were deemed insufficient. There is also a significant call for support from LGUs.

The analysis indicated a strong positive correlation between the three factors (applicability, awareness, and accessibility) of mental health services which suggests the potential for comprehensive improvements of mental health services through targeted programs.

Specifically, hotlines and emergency services are available, however, furthering the accessibility of these services via digital platforms is needed. Implementation of policies regarding mental health services is effective, but awareness campaigns can be further improved. Analysis indicates efficient coordinators for patient referrals, but there is insufficient allocation of funds for mental health initiatives.

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